

Magnetic nanoparticle formulations for early diagnosis of Alzheimer's disease

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Synthetic controls enable the precise manipulation of size, shape, composition, surface chemistry, and certain properties of nanoparticles during fabrication. Specifically, for magnetic nanoparticles (MNPs), key aspects correspond to tuning their magnetism following approaches to: a). Control size: Adjusting the size distribution of MNPs during synthesis, results in magnetic property tuning, b). Control composition: Varying the composition of MNPs can significantly influence their magnetic behavior i.e. magnetic moment, magnetic anisotropy, and Curie temperature. c). Modify surface: Can shield nanoparticles from agglomeration or specifically target biomedical probes and d). Control shape: The shape of MNPs also plays a critical role in determining their magnetic properties by adjusting the aspect ratio or geometry of the nanoparticles.

This work focuses on the synthesis, characterization and implementation of magnetite (Fe_3O_4) nanoparticles as carriers and enablers, in an electrochemical sensor for early diagnosis and monitoring of Alzheimer's disease (AD). These MNPs facilitate sample purification, minimize non-specific signals, and enhance flow control during various stages, such as bioreceptor incubation, purification, recognition, and signal acquisition.

Figure 1: Nanoparticle $\text{Au}/\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4$ schematic formulations and TEM images.

Magnetite MNPs of different sizes are synthesized following wet chemistry approaches and rigorously characterized structurally, morphologically, and magnetically (TEM, XRD, VSM). To provide electrochemical sensing biphasic nanostructures are manufactured composed of a gold contact and a magnetic part in variable formulations (Figure 1). Such nanostructures with diameters ranging from some tens of nm up to 200 nm are exploited for the immobilization of AD aptamers to eventually bind to AD blood biomarkers like $\text{A}\beta_{40}$, $\text{A}\beta_{42}$, and p-Tau with good selectivity, specificity, fast response, and low limits of detection (LOD), across different stages of AD.[1,2]

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[1] Devi, R. et al., *Nanoscale Advances*, 2(1), 239-248 (2020).

[2] Chiu, M. J. et al., *Nanomedicine: Nanotechnology, Biology and Medicine*, 28, 102182 (2020).